

FACTORS OF ADMINISTRATION, LEADERSHIP, AND MANAGEMENT SKILLS AS PREDICTORS OF SCHOOL PRINCIPAL'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The Philippine basic education system continues to face significant challenges, including limited facilities, overcrowded classrooms, and resource constraints, highlighting the essential role of effective school leadership in creating supportive learning environments and achieving educational goals. While school principals are expected to deliver strong outcomes, prior research has often treated administration, leadership, and management as broad categories without distinguishing which specific skills most influence performance. This study addressed that gap by examining the factors of administrative, leadership, and management skills as predictors of public elementary school principals' performance in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol for the school year 2023–2024. Using a descriptive-quantitative design, validated Likert-scale surveys measured principals' self-assessed skills, and official performance ratings were collected through the Office Performance Commitment Review Forms (OPCRF). Data from a randomly selected sample of 58 principals were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The findings revealed that principals generally demonstrated high levels of competence in administration, leadership, and management, especially in fostering collaborative, innovative, and well-managed school environments. While all skill domains were associated with strong overall performance ratings, the study emphasizes the value of balanced, strategic goal-setting and ongoing professional development to support principals in maintaining high standards of practice. These results highlight the importance of investing in leadership training, capacity-building, and collaborative learning to empower school leaders to drive sustainable improvements in basic education.

Keywords: *Administration, Basic Education, Leadership, Management, Performance, and Predictors*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine basic education system continues to face persistent and complex challenges, notably the lack of adequate school facilities, limited learning resources, and overcrowded classrooms. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), only 104,536 of the 327,851 school buildings nationwide are considered to be in good condition, underscoring the urgency of improving infrastructure and the overall learning environment (Hernando-Malipot, 2023). Recognizing these issues, Vice President and former Education Secretary Sara Duterte has emphasized the critical need for effective school leadership to navigate and address these systemic deficiencies. The Governance of Basic Education Act (Republic Act 9155) mandates that every school must be led by a principal or school head who holds the authority, responsibility, and accountability for achieving better learning outcomes. This includes leadership, management, teacher supervision, and maintaining student discipline.

In the Division of Bohol, the role of the school principal is especially critical in realizing the school's vision and mission, ensuring smooth operations, and managing governance functions (DepEd Bohol Division, 2023). Principals lead the implementation of programs and projects aimed at delivering quality basic education. Yet, despite this mandate, previous research has often treated administration, leadership, and management as broad, undifferentiated categories, lacking sufficient attention to the specific factors within each domain that drive school effectiveness. This research addresses that gap by investigating the distinct factors of administrative, leadership, and management skills as predictors of school principals' performance in elementary schools in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol.

Additionally, recent analyses highlight actionable measures that could help improve the Philippine education system. These include prioritizing infrastructure development, strengthening partnerships and collaboration among stakeholders, investing in faculty development, and hiring full-time nonteaching staff to support school operations (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). Such strategies underscore the need for capable, empowered principals who can effectively lead these initiatives within their schools.

Grounded in multiple theoretical perspectives, the study draws from Administrative Management Theory, Instrumental Leadership, and General Systems Theory. Henri Fayol's Administrative Management Theory (1916) provides the foundation for examining how school administrators organize, plan, and coordinate resources to improve efficiency and achieve educational goals (Gordon, 2023). John Antonakis and Robert J. House's Instrumental Leadership theory emphasizes the pragmatic, task-oriented aspects of leadership, such as setting direction, monitoring performance, and aligning team actions with goals (Antonakis & House, 2014). Meanwhile, General Systems Theory, as developed by Ludwig von Bertalanffy, underscores the need to view schools as open

systems that integrate human, material, and methodological resources to provide quality education (von Bertalanffy, 1970; Elujekwute, 2019). Together, these theories frame the understanding of how administrative, leadership, and management skills function as interconnected, yet distinct, domains influencing school performance.

A nuanced understanding of these domains is essential given the multi-faceted role of school principals. Effective administration involves the strategic arrangement and coordination of educational resources to ensure adequate inputs, oversee implementation progress, and achieve desired educational outcomes (Amadi, 2008). School administrators face challenges such as resource shortages, large class sizes, and limited infrastructure—issues that demand careful planning, resource allocation, and mentoring of teaching staff to maintain a conducive learning environment (Al-Samarrai, 2016; Oke, 2016). Management skills, by contrast, focus on operational efficiency, monitoring performance, setting targets, and people management. Research suggests that effective school management practices are closely linked to improved learning outcomes, particularly in low- and middle-income contexts (Bloom et al., 2015; Gautam, 2023). Principals who exhibit strong management skills can optimize daily operations, use data to inform decisions, and ensure accountability within the school system.

Leadership skills, meanwhile, go beyond technical coordination to inspire and guide the school community. Principals with strong leadership capabilities build a shared vision, support teachers' professional growth, and model effective practices that foster a positive school climate (Grissom et al., 2021). Effective leadership is associated with improved teacher satisfaction, higher student achievement, and enhanced school effectiveness (Sebastian et al., 2016; Shaked, 2023). This interactive, interdependent approach requires principals to balance authority with empathy, empowering teachers through mentorship, collaboration, and professional development opportunities (Hollingworth et al., 2018).

In the Philippine context, these roles and responsibilities are further guided by legal frameworks such as the Education Act (Batas Pambansa Blg. 232) and DepEd's Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). Under Section 12 of the Education Act, school administrators are granted sufficient administrative discretion necessary for the efficient and effective performance of their functions, while the RPMS provides a standardized framework for assessing principals' performance through the Office Performance Commitment Review Forms (OPCRF) (DepEd, 2015; DepEd Division of Bohol, 2024). This study adopts the OPCRf as the primary tool for measuring the performance of school principals in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol for the school year 2023–2024.

By systematically examining the specific factors within administrative, leadership, and management skills, this research aims to provide evidence-based insights that can inform leadership training, professional development, and policy planning in basic education. Such an approach not only addresses the urgent challenges faced by the Philippine education system but also contributes to the broader goal of fostering effective,

accountable, and responsive school leadership capable of driving meaningful educational change.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the factors of administrative, leadership, and management skills as predictors of the performance of school principals in DepEd elementary schools in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol for the school year 2023-2024.

Particularly, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of administrative skills of the school principals in terms of:
 - 1.1. educational Resource Input;
 - 1.2. educational Implement Progress; and
 - 1.3. educational objective outcome?
2. What is the level of leadership skills of the school principals in terms of:
 - 2.1. builds a Vision;
 - 2.2. provides Support;
 - 2.3. manages Teachers' Professional Development;
 - 2.4. modeling?
3. What is the level of management skills of the school principals in terms of:
 - 3.1. operations;
 - 3.2. monitoring;
 - 3.3. target Setting;
 - 3.4. people management?
4. What is the school principal's performance rating in the school year 2023-2024?
5. Do educational resource input, educational implement progress, educational objective outcome, builds a vision, provides support, manages teachers' professional development, modeling operations, monitoring, target setting, and people management predict the performance rating of the school principal?
6. What is the most parsimonious combination of educational resource input, educational implement progress. educational objective outcome, builds a vision, provides support, manages teachers' professional development, modeling operations, monitoring, target setting, and people management in predicting the performance rating of the school principal?
7. Do administrative, management, and leadership skills predict the performance rating of the school principal?
8. What program can be proposed based on the results of this study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-quantitative method to investigate the associations among the administrative, leadership, and management skills of DepEd elementary school principals and the principals' performance in the 3rd Congressional District of the Division of Bohol for the school year 2023–2024.

Quantitative methods were used to assess the self-assessments of the school principals in terms of their administrative, leadership, and management skills. Likert scale surveys or questionnaires were utilized to gather quantitative data on how principals perceived their skills in these areas, allowing for numerical analysis.

Additionally, quantitative data such as the principals' performance ratings were collected through the OPCRf ratings of the school principals for the school year 2023–2024.

Research Environment

The study was conducted within the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, specifically focusing on the 3rd Congressional District of the Province of Bohol. This district included the municipalities of Alicia, Anda, Batuan, Bilar, Candijay, Carmen, Dimiao, Duero, Garcia Hernandez, Guindulman, Jagna, Lila, Loay, Loboc, Mabini, Pilar, Sevilla, Sierra Bullones, and Valencia. The 3rd Congressional District had the largest number of municipalities among the three districts in Bohol. This increased the chance of capturing a more representative sample and reduced bias. In addition, this helped to prevent skewed or homogenous data, leading to more accurate results.

Research Respondents

There were 140 officially designated public elementary school principals in the entire 3rd Congressional District of Bohol. Out of the 140, the sample was randomly selected using a randomizer in Excel. A minimum sample size of 58 was used to achieve a 95% confidence level and an α error probability of 0.1.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants had to be currently employed in a public elementary school within the 3rd Congressional District of the Division of Bohol and officially designated as school principals. They were required to have at least one year of experience working as a school principal in a public school.

Exclusion Criteria

Principals or school heads working in private elementary schools were not included. In addition, those with less than one year of experience as a public elementary school principal were excluded from the study.

Withdrawal Criteria

Participants were allowed to withdraw from the study at any time without facing repercussions. Additionally, their participation was entirely voluntary, and they could choose to discontinue their involvement without any impact on their professional standing.

Research Instrument

This study employed an instrument drawn from three separate standardized research questionnaires specifically designed to investigate the skills of elementary school principals in the identified district. The first part of the instrument involved an inquiry into the school principals' Office Performance Commitment and Review (OPCR) overall rating.

The second part of the instrument was anchored in the standardized questionnaire of Weng et al. (2024). It sought to describe the school principals' perceptions of their administrative skills by asking them to respond according to their degree of agreement on a five-point Likert scale. It included 24 statements distributed across three dimensions: educational resource input (six statements), educational implementation progress (ten statements), and educational objective outcome (eight statements). The instrument's effectiveness was ensured through a four-phase research procedure implemented as follows: Phase I synthesized and established a preliminary framework of the scale and interview outlines based on a thorough review of the literature. Phase II involved conducting interviews with school administrators and analyzing key items in the conversations to evaluate and refine the preliminary scale. Phase III validated and finalized the refined scale through expert validity surveys and a pilot test. Phase IV implemented the final (or formal) test using the revised scale to gather raw data, which was then analyzed using various statistical instruments (Weng et al., 2024).

The third part of the instrument was anchored in the study of McNally et al. (2024), which adapted the World Management Survey (WMS) method previously applied in schools (Bloom et al., 2015). This section sought to describe the principals' perceptions of their management skills using a five-point Likert scale. It included 18 statements distributed across four dimensions: operations (four statements), monitoring (four statements), target setting (five statements), and people management (five statements). The validation and reliability of the questionnaire were meticulously ensured through a comprehensive process. The survey instrument was carefully designed, likely drawing on established methodologies such as the WMS due to its prior use and validation in similar contexts. Additionally, interviewers tasked with administering the survey underwent rigorous training, including guidance from external experts familiar with the WMS methodology. This training equipped interviewers with a deep understanding of the theoretical frameworks and best practices associated with the survey, contributing to successful validation and reliability testing (McNally et al., 2024).

The fourth part of the instrument was anchored in the standardized questionnaire of Liu et al. (2024) and was also used in the study by Tayag (2018). This section sought to describe the principals' perceptions of their leadership skills using a five-point Likert scale. It consisted of 23 statements distributed across four dimensions: building a vision (six statements), providing support (six statements), managing teachers' professional development (six statements), and modeling (five statements). The internal consistency of the questionnaire with Filipino respondents was established through reliability analysis, which demonstrated high to excellent reliability (Tayag, 2018).

The researcher conducted a reliability test with 30 participants to ensure the consistency and stability of the measurements or instruments utilized in the study. This strengthened the overall reliability and credibility of the study's results. Overall, the instrument served as the primary tool for gathering quantitative data and was distributed to the selected sample of elementary school principals within the study's scope. Participants were encouraged to provide accurate and honest responses to each item to ensure the reliability and validity of the collected data.

Research Procedure

This study followed ethical standards by ensuring respondent confidentiality, privacy, and voluntary participation. Permission was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study, particularly for gathering the principals' performance ratings. In addition, the researcher requested the list of principals of the public elementary schools in the 3rd District of Bohol, including the relevant information necessary to identify the participants. In this study, surveys and OPCR ratings were collected.

Participants were approached and given time to consider their involvement. The researcher explained and emphasized the confidential nature of the study, especially regarding the data to be gathered. Specifically, the researcher requested the performance ratings of the principals and gave them assurance that this information would be handled with utmost confidentiality. Participants were assured that the data gathered would be stored collectively to anonymize them. In addition, no personal information was shared publicly. To ensure confidentiality, the names of the principals were not identified in the survey instruments or in the data. The completed instruments were collected directly by the researcher. Only the researcher and authorized personnel handled the responses, ensuring that their answers remained private. The data was used solely for this study.

In addition, the researcher made it clear to participants that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any moment without any consequences. The researcher explained the purpose of the survey to build trust and create a comfortable environment. The benefits included personal reflection and contributions to educational improvements. Before obtaining the performance ratings of the principals, consent was obtained from both the Division Office and the principals themselves. These protocols

were clearly stated in the informed consent. Moreover, participants received a token of appreciation.

The study lasted about five months, with data collection taking approximately two months and surveys estimated to require around 20 minutes each. Participants were informed of the timeframe and the importance of their responses.

After the data was used, it was disposed of by shredding, making it impossible to reconstruct. These procedures adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and complied with the approval of the Holy Name University Ethics Review Committee.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as the mean and standard deviation of responses were used in determining the following: the level of administrative skills of the school principals in terms of Educational Resource Input, Educational Implement Progress, and Educational Objective Outcome; the level of leadership skills of school principals in terms of Builds a Vision, Provides Support, Manages Teachers' Professional Development, and Modeling, and the level of management skills of the school principals in terms of Operations, Monitoring, Target Setting and People Management.

The description of the 5-point scale was from the Strategic Performance Rating Scale, which is used to describe the level of a principal's skills (Mindanao State University, 2012). This includes Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor.

Each aspect of the administrative, leadership and management skills was rated using a 5-point Likert scale, with interpretation ranged as follows: 1.00–1.49 (Very Low), 1.50–2.49 (Low), 2.50–3.49 (Moderate), 3.50–4.49 (High), and 4.50–5.00 (Very High),

In addition, regression analysis was used to determine the predictors of the school principal's performance rating. Jamovi software was used to analyze the data that predicts the performance rating and identify the most parsimonious combination of variables that predicts the principal's performance rating.

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered in the study. It provides a detailed account of the findings on the levels of administrative, management, and leadership skills of public elementary school principals in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol, as well as their corresponding performance ratings.

The study employed a five-point scale adapted from the Strategic Performance Rating Scale developed by Mindanao State University (2012), which describes the level of the principals' skills. The scale includes the categories: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, and Poor.

This rating scale formed part of the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) developed by MSU. The SPMS was designed to align individual performance with organizational goals and mandates, serving as a tool to foster continuous improvement, enhance productivity, and ensure objective ratings for personnel actions, incentives, and sanctions. In this study, it served as a structured metric for systematically analyzing principals' effectiveness. It provided a consistent framework for interpreting their administrative, management, and leadership capabilities based on respondents' evaluations.

Table 1.1
Level of Administrative Skills of School Principal in terms of Educational Resource Input

Educational Resource Input	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
Members of my school can enjoy using facilities in a welcoming environment.	4.79	0.41	Outstanding
The condition of the school has been well maintained due to good administration.	4.48	0.50	Very Satisfactory
The distribution and application of resources in my school have been fair and effective.	4.81	0.39	Outstanding
The faculty and staff of my school have demonstrated a stronger competency in the use and application of technology than before.	4.47	0.50	Very Satisfactory
I believe that the buildings/constructions within my school can unobtrusively influence people.	4.34	0.51	Very Satisfactory
I believe that the atmosphere in my school is open and creative.	4.60	0.49	Outstanding

Table 1.1 presents the participants' perceptions of their principals' administrative skills in terms of educational resource input. Overall, the ratings indicate a high level of competency in this domain, with most indicators interpreted as Outstanding or Very Satisfactory.

The highest-rated factor was *"The distribution and application of resources in my school have been fair and effective"* ($\bar{X} = 4.81$, $SD = 0.39$), suggesting strong agreement among participants that resources are allocated and utilized efficiently under the school principal's administration. Similarly, *"Members of my school can enjoy using facilities in a welcoming environment"* ($\bar{X} = 4.79$, $SD = 0.41$) and *"The atmosphere in my school is open and creative"* ($\bar{X} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.49$) also received Outstanding ratings, indicating that principals effectively foster a positive, engaging environment conducive to learning.

Very Satisfactory ratings were observed for factors related to *school maintenance* ($\bar{X} = 4.48$, $SD = 0.50$), *faculty and staff competency in technology use* ($\bar{X} = 4.47$, $SD = 0.50$), and *the influence of school buildings on people* ($\bar{X} = 4.34$, $SD = 0.51$). These results suggest that while principals demonstrate strong administrative skills in these areas, there remains room for improvement, particularly in enhancing technological competencies and ensuring the physical environment continues to positively influence stakeholders.

Overall, the findings highlight that school principals exhibited a commendable level of administrative skill in managing educational resources, ensuring fair distribution, maintaining facilities, and fostering a welcoming and productive learning environment. However, targeted efforts to further strengthen school maintenance practices and technological integration could enhance their overall effectiveness even further.

Table 1.2
Level of Administrative Skills of School Principal in terms of Educational Implement Progress

Educational Implement Progress	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
In my school, my deeds are supported by all my colleagues.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I embrace stronger collaborative interactions to create a more intimate workplace.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I encourage teachers to contribute to the creation and amendment of school policy.	4.60	0.49	Outstanding
I always encourage teachers to innovate teaching.	4.71	0.46	Outstanding
In my school, members of different departments support one another to achieve personal and professional outcomes.	4.57	0.50	Outstanding
The faculties have a consensus to cooperate and help one another.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding
I believe that the overall planning of schools and facilities can meet teachers' needs of teaching.	4.60	0.49	Outstanding
Faculties usually approach and overcome team challenges in a joyful atmosphere.	4.52	0.50	Outstanding
Over time, my administrative effectiveness has gradually improved within the school.	4.45	0.50	Very Satisfactory
My administration is well structured and procedures are clear and defined.	4.47	0.50	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.2 illustrates the perceived level of administrative skills of school principals in terms of Educational Implement Progress. Overall, the findings indicate a high level of administrative effectiveness, with most factors receiving Outstanding ratings.

The highest-rated factor was *"I always encourage teachers to innovate teaching"* ($\bar{X} = 4.71$, $SD = 0.46$), indicating that school principals strongly promote creativity and instructional improvements among teachers. Additionally, principals were perceived as highly effective in fostering collaborative interactions ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.49$) and ensuring that faculty members support one another in achieving professional and personal goals ($\bar{X} = 4.57$, $SD = 0.50$). These results suggest that principals excel in building a positive, cooperative, and innovative educational environment.

Moreover, the data reflects principals' strong advocacy for participatory decision-making, as shown by the Outstanding ratings for *encouraging teachers to contribute to*

the creation and amendment of school policy ($\bar{X} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.49$) and *ensuring that school planning aligns with teachers' needs* ($\bar{X} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.49$). This highlights that school leaders actively involve educators in shaping institutional strategies, fostering a sense of ownership and engagement among teachers.

Table 1.3
Level of Administrative Skills of School Principal in terms of Educational Objective Outcome

Educational Objective Outcome	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
The results show that learners have progressed in their studies.	4.41	0.49	Very Satisfactory
The learners have shown improvements in their behavior.	4.41	0.49	Very Satisfactory
The learning environment of the school is quite good.	4.48	0.50	Very Satisfactory
The relationship between the learners and teachers is harmonious.	4.66	0.48	Outstanding
Parents and teachers experience positive interactions and better communication.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I believe that the entire pedagogic effectiveness of teachers is quite good.	4.57	0.50	Outstanding
Members of the local community appreciate and support our teaching habits and administration.	4.55	0.50	Outstanding
I believe that parents are satisfied with the overall performance of the school.	4.45	0.50	Very Satisfactory

Table 1.3 reflects the perceived level of administrative skills of school principals in achieving Educational Objective Outcomes. The overall findings suggest that school principals are highly effective in ensuring positive educational results, as indicated by the mix of Outstanding and Very Satisfactory ratings.

The highest-rated factor is "The relationship between the learners and teachers is harmonious" ($\bar{X} = 4.66$, $SD = 0.48$), highlighting that school principals have successfully fostered a positive and supportive teacher-student relationship, which is essential for effective learning. Similarly, strong parent-teacher communication ($\bar{X} = 4.62$, $SD = 0.49$), pedagogic effectiveness ($\bar{X} = 4.57$, $SD = 0.50$), and community support ($\bar{X} = 4.55$, $SD = 0.50$) all received Outstanding ratings. These findings indicate that school leaders excel in strengthening collaboration among students, teachers, parents, and the local community, contributing to a well-rounded educational environment.

The factors that received Very Satisfactory ratings include student academic progress ($\bar{X} = 4.41$, $SD = 0.49$), student behavior improvement ($\bar{X} = 4.41$, $SD = 0.49$), school learning environment ($\bar{X} = 4.48$, $SD = 0.50$), and parent satisfaction ($\bar{X} = 4.45$, $SD = 0.50$). These ratings suggest that while principals are effective in ensuring student development, school atmosphere, and parental approval, there is still room for enhancement in these areas. Specifically, strategies aimed at further improving student

academic performance and behavior management may help elevate these aspects to an Outstanding level.

The data suggests that school principals demonstrate a strong level of administrative competency in achieving educational objectives, particularly in maintaining positive teacher-student relationships, effective teaching strategies, and strong parent-community engagement. However, efforts to further enhance student progress, behavior, and parental satisfaction may help optimize their leadership impact.

Table 2.1
Level of Management Skills of School Principals in terms of Operations

Operations	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I make sure that materials and practices are standardized and aligned to be capable of moving learners through learning pathways over time and ensuring to meet the needs of teachers and learners.	4.55	0.50	Outstanding
I encourage teachers to have flexibility in teaching methods and learner involvement ensuring learning objectives are met.	4.72	0.45	Outstanding
I use assessment to verify learning outcomes at critical stages, make data easily available, and use it intelligently to adapt learner strategies	4.60	0.49	Outstanding
I ignite teachers to incorporate teaching best practices and the sharing of these resources into the classroom.	4.66	0.48	Outstanding

Table 2.1 presents the self-assessed management skills of school principals in overseeing operations, with particular focus on ensuring standardized materials, flexible teaching methods, assessment-driven strategies, and the integration of best teaching practices.

The highest-rated skill was “*encouraging teachers to have flexibility in teaching methods and learner involvement*” ($\bar{X} = 4.72$, $SD = 0.45$), indicating that principals strongly promote adaptive teaching strategies while ensuring that learning objectives are effectively met. “*Incorporating teaching best practices and resource sharing*” followed closely with a mean score of 4.66 ($SD = 0.48$), reflecting principals’ active role in fostering a collaborative and innovative teaching environment.

Additionally, “*using assessment data to verify learning outcomes and adapt strategies*” received a mean score of 4.60 ($SD = 0.49$), highlighting principals’ commitment to data-driven decision-making to enhance student learning. The lowest-rated factor—though still within the Outstanding category—was “*ensuring that materials and practices are standardized and aligned with learning pathways*”, with a mean score of 4.55 ($SD = 0.50$). This suggests that while principals maintain strong practices in this area, there remains room for further improvement in aligning resources with long-term learning goals.

Overall, with all mean scores falling within the Outstanding category, the results indicate that school principals demonstrate a high level of competency in operational management, particularly in fostering flexible, effective teaching strategies while maintaining standardization and assessment-based improvements.

Table 2.2
Level of Management Skills of School Principals in terms of Monitoring

Monitoring	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I implement process documentation and continuous improvement.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding
I make sure that school performance is measured with appropriate methods and frequency and communicated effectively to teachers and other concerned stakeholders.	4.55	0.50	Outstanding
I make sure that school performance is reviewed with appropriate frequency and follow-up.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding
I believe that differing rates of school performance (not only individual teacher performance) lead to different consequences.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding

Table 2.2 presents the level of management skills of school principals in terms of monitoring, highlighting their commitment to process documentation, performance measurement, and continuous improvement.

The highest-rated factor was “*ensuring that school performance is measured with appropriate methods and frequency and effectively communicated to teachers and other stakeholders*” ($\bar{X} = 4.55$, $SD = 0.50$). This indicates that principals prioritize clear and consistent communication regarding school performance outcomes.

The other three factors—“*implementing process documentation and continuous improvement*,” “*reviewing school performance with appropriate frequency and follow-up*,” and “*recognizing that varying school performance levels lead to different consequences*”—each received a mean score of 4.53 ($SD = 0.50$). These results suggest that while school principals demonstrate outstanding competency in monitoring processes, there remains opportunity for further enhancement in strategies for performance review and adaptation.

Overall, the findings confirm that principals maintain a high level of effectiveness in monitoring school performance, ensuring that evaluation methods are systematic, transparent, and geared toward continuous development.

Table 2.3
Level of Management Skills of School Principals in terms of Target Setting

Target Setting	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
There is a system that tracks meaningful targets tied to learner outcomes.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding
The school and individual targets are aligned with each other and the overall system goals.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I have a rational approach to planning and setting targets.	4.45	0.50	Very Satisfactory
I make sure that targets are appropriately difficult to achieve.	4.03	0.93	Very Satisfactory
I ensure that performance measures are understandable and that performance is openly communicated.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding

Table 2.3 presents the level of management skills of school principals in terms of target setting, emphasizing their ability to establish and track meaningful goals aligned with learner outcomes and institutional objectives.

The highest-rated factors—“*school and individual targets are aligned with system-wide goals*” and “*performance measures are clear and openly communicated*”—both received mean scores of 4.62 (SD = 0.49). This suggests that principals ensure coherence between institutional objectives and individual teacher or student targets, while maintaining transparency in performance assessments.

The factor “*presence of a system that tracks meaningful targets tied to learner outcomes*” received a mean score of 4.53 (SD = 0.50), indicating a strong commitment to effectively monitoring progress. Meanwhile, “*a rational approach to planning and setting targets*” was rated Very Satisfactory, with a mean score of 4.45 (SD = 0.50), suggesting room for further refinement in strategic planning practices.

The lowest-rated factor—“*ensuring that targets are appropriately difficult to achieve*”—received a mean score of 4.03 (SD = 0.93). While this still indicates that targets are set with appropriate challenge in mind, it suggests inconsistencies in the level of difficulty, highlighting an area that may benefit from further attention.

Overall, the findings indicate that school principals demonstrate outstanding competency in aligning goals and communicating performance measures, while also recognizing opportunities for improvement in setting targets that are appropriately challenging and achievable.

Table 2.4
Level of Management Skills of School Principals in terms of People Management

People Management	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I make sure that good teacher performance is rewarded and appreciated.	4.69	0.46	Outstanding
I can deal with underperformers.	4.52	0.56	Outstanding
I guarantee that promotions and career progression are based on performance.	4.67	0.47	Outstanding
I identify and target needed teaching, leadership, and other capacity in the school.	4.57	0.50	Outstanding
I will go out of my way to keep the high-performing teachers.	4.57	0.59	Outstanding

Table 2.4 presents the level of management skills of school principals in terms of people management, highlighting their ability to recognize and develop teacher performance within the school.

The highest-rated factor, “*ensuring that good teacher performance is rewarded and appreciated*,” received a mean score of 4.69 (SD = 0.46), indicating a strong commitment to fostering a culture of recognition and motivation. Similarly, “*guaranteeing that promotions and career progression are based on performance*” was rated 4.67 (SD = 0.47), emphasizing a merit-based approach to career advancement within the institution.

The factors “*identifying and targeting needed teaching, leadership, and other capacities in the school*” and “*making efforts to retain high-performing teachers*” both received mean scores of 4.57, demonstrating that principals actively work to build and sustain a competent workforce.

The ability to “*deal with underperformers*” was rated 4.52 (SD = 0.56). While still within the Outstanding category, this suggests a slightly greater challenge in effectively addressing performance issues.

Overall, the findings indicate that school principals excel in people management by rewarding excellence, promoting merit-based career growth, and ensuring that skilled educators remain within the institution, while also addressing underperformance when necessary.

Table 3.1
Level of Leadership Skills of School Principals in terms of Building a Vision

Building a Vision	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I set a clear vision for teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders.	4.66	0.48	Outstanding
I communicate the vision with the teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders.	4.64	0.48	Outstanding

I demonstrate high expectations for teachers, learners.	4.60	0.49	Outstanding
I provide useful assistance to teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders in working towards the vision set.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I encourage teachers to develop individual goals consistent with school goals.	4.53	0.50	Outstanding
I help to clarify the reasons for implementing the vision to teachers, learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	4.59	0.49	Outstanding

Table 3.1 presents the level of leadership skills of school principals in terms of building a vision, emphasizing their ability to set and communicate a clear direction for the school community.

The highest-rated factor, *“setting a clear vision for teachers, learners, parents, and other stakeholders,”* received a mean score of 4.66 (SD = 0.48), reflecting principals’ strong commitment to establishing a well-defined educational direction. *“Communicating this vision effectively”* followed closely with a mean score of 4.64, underscoring the importance of ensuring that all stakeholders understand and align with the school’s goals.

“Demonstrating high expectations for teachers and learners” received a mean score of 4.60, indicating principals’ dedication to fostering a culture of excellence. Additionally, *“providing useful assistance to stakeholders in working towards the vision”* was rated 4.62, highlighting the supportive role principals play in helping the school community achieve set goals.

“Encouraging teachers to develop individual goals consistent with school objectives” was rated 4.53, emphasizing the effort to create coherence between personal and institutional growth. Lastly, *“helping to clarify the reasons for implementing the vision”* received a mean score of 4.59, further demonstrating principals’ commitment to ensuring stakeholder understanding and buy-in.

Overall, the findings indicate that school principals excel in building and communicating a strong educational vision, ensuring alignment and collaboration among all members of the school community.

Table 3.2
Level of Leadership Skills of School Principals in terms of Providing Support

Providing Support	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I provide resources (time, money, and training opportunities) to better support the overall development of the school.	4.76	0.43	Outstanding

I facilitate opportunities (demonstration lessons and training projects) for staff to learn from each other.	4.71	0.46	Outstanding
I reward teachers who engage in ongoing teacher-professional learning.	4.72	0.45	Outstanding
I encourage ongoing teacher professional learning to implement new ideas and practices.	4.71	0.46	Outstanding
I support an open and supportive environment for staff to communicate.	4.74	0.44	Outstanding
I make teachers feel appreciated for their contributions to school improvement.	4.76	0.43	Outstanding

Table 3.2 highlights the high level of leadership skills demonstrated by school principals in providing support to their teachers and staff. All factors received an Outstanding rating, reflecting principals' strong commitment to fostering a supportive and growth-oriented school environment.

The highest-rated factors were “*providing resources such as time, money, and training opportunities*” ($\bar{X} = 4.76$, $SD = 0.43$) and “*making teachers feel appreciated for their contributions*” ($\bar{X} = 4.76$, $SD = 0.43$). These results suggest that school leaders actively invest in both material and emotional support to enhance school development and motivate teachers.

Other notable strengths include “*rewarding teachers for engaging in professional learning*” ($\bar{X} = 4.72$, $SD = 0.45$) and “*facilitating peer learning opportunities through demonstration lessons and training projects*” ($\bar{X} = 4.71$, $SD = 0.46$). These findings indicate that principals not only encourage continuous learning but also create structures that promote collaboration and professional growth.

Additionally, school principals were rated highly for “*promoting open communication among staff*” ($\bar{X} = 4.74$, $SD = 0.44$) and “*encouraging the implementation of new teaching ideas and practices*” ($\bar{X} = 4.71$, $SD = 0.46$). This underscores their role in creating an inclusive and innovative learning environment that supports staff engagement and instructional improvement.

Table 3.3
Level of Leadership Skills of School Principals in terms of Management of Teachers' Professional Development

Management of Teachers' Professional Development	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I guide teachers in their professional development.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I design a systematic evaluation system to assess the impact of teachers' professional development in the teaching and learning process.	4.47	0.50	Very Satisfactory

I diversify the process of achieving any goal to arouse teachers' interest.	4.55	0.50	Outstanding
I promote professional learning content to fit teachers' needs.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding
I emphasize the purpose of professional learning for teaching improvement.	4.57	0.50	Outstanding
I make regular visits to ensure systematic monitoring of teacher professional learning	4.53	0.50	Outstanding

Table 3.3 presents the level of leadership skills of school principals in managing teachers' professional development, highlighting their role in guiding and supporting educators in their continuous growth.

The highest-rated factors—“*guiding teachers in their professional development*” and “*promoting professional learning content to fit teachers' needs*”—both received mean scores of 4.62 (SD = 0.49). These results reflect principals' strong commitment to fostering teacher growth.

“*Emphasizing the purpose of professional learning for teaching improvement*” received a mean score of 4.57, indicating the importance principals place on linking professional development with instructional effectiveness. “*Diversifying the process of achieving goals to arouse teachers' interest*” followed with a mean score of 4.55, demonstrating efforts to engage teachers in meaningful learning experiences.

“*Systematic monitoring of teacher professional learning through regular visits*” was rated 4.53, reinforcing the significance of direct supervision and ongoing support. Meanwhile, “*designing a systematic evaluation system to assess the impact of professional development*” received a slightly lower rating of 4.47, categorized as Very Satisfactory, suggesting an area where further improvement may be beneficial.

Overall, the results suggest that school principals excel in facilitating professional development by guiding, engaging, and monitoring teachers while ensuring that professional learning aligns with instructional goals.

Table 3.4
Level of Leadership Skills of School Principals in terms of Modeling

Modeling	\bar{X}	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
I display energy and enthusiasm in doing any task.	4.71	0.46	Outstanding
I demonstrate a willingness to share my achievements with teachers.	4.74	0.44	Outstanding
I show outstanding performance in being a leader and a team player.	4.55	0.50	Outstanding
I focus on the latest ideas in the teaching and learning process.	4.62	0.49	Outstanding

I have my own unique opinions about teaching and learning.	4.57	0.50	Outstanding
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Table 3.4 presents the level of leadership skills of school principals in terms of modeling, emphasizing their ability to serve as role models for teachers.

The highest-rated factor, “*demonstrating a willingness to share achievements with teachers*,” received a mean score of 4.74 (SD = 0.44), highlighting principals’ openness and collaborative leadership approach. “*Displaying energy and enthusiasm in performing tasks*” followed closely with a rating of 4.71, indicating principals’ dedication and motivation in carrying out their responsibilities.

“*Focusing on the latest ideas in the teaching and learning process*” was rated 4.62, reflecting principals’ commitment to staying updated with educational advancements. “*Having unique opinions about teaching and learning*” received a mean score of 4.57, showing that principals bring individuality and innovation to their leadership style.

Meanwhile, “*showing outstanding performance as both a leader and a team player*” received a score of 4.55, reinforcing the importance of balancing leadership and collaboration within the school environment.

Overall, the results suggest that school principals effectively model exemplary leadership behaviors by maintaining enthusiasm, embracing innovation, sharing achievements, and fostering teamwork within their institutions.

Table 4
The School Principal’s Performance Rating

Performance Rating	Adjectival Rating	Frequency	Percentage
4.500-5.000	Outstanding	11	18.97
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	47	81.03
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory	0	0
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0
Below 1.499	Poor	0	0
TOTAL		58	100
Standard Deviation			0.1110657

The performance rating of school principals, as shown in Table 4, indicates that most principals received a "Very Satisfactory" rating, with 47 out of 58 principals (81.03%) falling within the 3.500–4.499 range. Meanwhile, 11 principals (18.97%) achieved an "Outstanding" rating, scoring between 4.500 and 5.000.

Notably, no principal received ratings categorized as "Satisfactory," "Unsatisfactory," or "Poor," indicating that all evaluated principals performed at a

commendable level. The standard deviation of 0.111 suggests low variability in performance ratings, meaning the scores are closely clustered around the mean.

These results highlight a consistently high level of performance among school principals, demonstrating a strong inclination toward excellence in fulfilling their roles and responsibilities.

Table 5
Predictors of School Principal Performance

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p	Interpretation
Intercept	4.2365	0.2506	16.982	< .001	Significant baseline
Educational Resource Input	-0.0849	0.0734	-1.157	0.253	Not significant
Educational Implement Progress	0.0489	0.1027	0.476	0.636	Not significant
Educational Objective Outcome	0.1058	0.0883	1.198	0.237	Not significant
Operations	-0.0145	0.0928	-0.156	0.877	Not significant
Monitoring	0.1144	0.0750	1.526	0.134	Not significant
Target Setting	-0.1840	0.0910	-2.022	0.049	Significant
People Management	0.0580	0.0701	0.827	0.411	Not significant
Builds a Vision	0.0161	0.0844	0.198	0.850	Not significant
Provides Support	-0.0379	0.0825	-0.460	0.648	Not significant
Manages Teachers' Professional Development	0.0885	0.0763	1.160	0.252	Not significant
Modeling	-0.0692	0.0640	-1.082	0.285	Not significant

The multiple linear regression analysis conducted in this study aimed to explore the relationships between several predictor variables and school principal performance, as measured through a structured questionnaire.

The results revealed that only target setting demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with performance ($p = 0.049$), suggesting a negative association in which higher levels of target setting are linked to lower performance outcomes. This negative relationship indicates that overly rigid or unrealistic targets may cause stress or hinder principal performance.

The model also showed that all other predictor variables—including educational resource input, educational implementation progress, educational objective outcome, operations, monitoring, people management, vision setting, providing support, managing teachers' professional development, and modeling—did not demonstrate statistically significant relationships with performance ($p > 0.05$).

Moreover, the positive t-values for many of these variables suggest potential positive relationships with principal performance. For example, *educational*

implementation progress ($t = 0.476$, $p = 0.636$) reflects the idea that progress in implementing strategies such as promoting collaboration and involving teachers in policy creation may enhance principal performance. Similarly, *educational objective outcomes* ($t = 1.198$, $p = 0.237$), which involve achieving goals like improved student behavior and academic progress, show a positive trend, though not statistically significant.

Monitoring ($t = 1.526$, $p = 0.134$) is also expected to positively influence performance by effectively tracking school progress. The weak positive relationship observed for *people management* ($t = 0.827$, $p = 0.413$) suggests that effectively recognizing high-performing teachers and addressing underperformance may have a positive impact. Similarly, *vision setting* ($t = 0.190$, $p = 0.850$) shows a very weak positive relationship, while *managing teachers' professional development* ($t = 1.160$, $p = 0.252$) also indicates a positive trend.

On the other hand, negative t-values point to an inverse relationship between certain predictor variables and principal performance. For example, *educational resource input* ($t = -1.157$, $p = 0.253$) suggests that simply providing more resources does not automatically improve performance unless they are strategically utilized. This underscores the importance of not just providing resources, such as well-maintained facilities or advanced technology, but using them effectively to support educational goals.

Similarly, *operations* ($t = -0.156$, $p = 0.877$) showed a negative relationship, suggesting these practices may not have a significant impact on principal performance.

Importantly, *target setting* ($t = -2.022$, $p = 0.049$) was the only statistically significant negative predictor, reinforcing the idea that unrealistic or overly demanding targets can hinder principal performance. Additionally, *providing support* ($t = -0.460$, $p = 0.648$) and *modeling* ($t = -1.082$, $p = 0.285$) also demonstrated negative relationships, suggesting that general support or role modeling alone may not be sufficient to enhance performance. These results imply that more structured and targeted support mechanisms, as well as specific leadership actions beyond general role modeling, are necessary to foster principal effectiveness.

Research Question Number 6 was also addressed through Table 5, which showed that there is no parsimonious combination of the constructs—educational resource input, educational implementation progress, educational objective outcome, building a vision, providing support, managing teachers' professional development, modeling, operations, monitoring, target setting, and people management—in predicting the performance rating of school principals. Based on the data, the only construct that could predict performance was target setting, and even this demonstrated a negative association. This suggests that as target setting increases, predicted performance decreases, and vice versa.

This finding aligns with the study by Newman and Azevedo (2013), which suggests that setting excessively high-performance targets can foster resentment among staff, ultimately weakening the system's credibility and negatively impacting future productivity. Consequently, this dynamic could lead to an unfavorable perception of school principal

performance. Furthermore, they emphasized that when targets are perceived as impossible to achieve, principals may either disregard them or engage in unethical practices, thereby compromising the integrity of the performance management system.

Tabel 6
Administrative, Management, and Leadership Skills as Predictors of Principals' Performance

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p	Interpretation
Intercept	4.2045	0.2098	20.040	< .001	Significant baseline
Administrative Skills	0.0492	0.1098	0.448	0.656	Not significant
Management Skills	-0.0782	0.0882	-0.886	0.379	Not significant
Leadership Skills	0.0763	0.1003	0.760	0.450	Not significant

As shown in Table 6, the results reveal that none of the three main skill domains—administrative skills ($p = 0.656$), management skills ($p = 0.379$), and leadership skills ($p = 0.450$)—significantly predict the performance rating of school principals, as all p -values are greater than 0.05.

While administrative and leadership skills show slight positive effects on performance ratings, and management skills show a slight negative effect, these relationships are not statistically significant. This suggests that, within this study's context, none of these skill domains independently explain variation in principal performance ratings in a meaningful way.

Findings

Based on the analysis of data gathered from public elementary school principals in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol, the following findings were established in response to the specific research questions:

1. Level of Administrative Skills of School Principals. School principals demonstrated a high level of administrative skills overall. In terms of *educational resource input*, they effectively ensured equitable distribution and efficient use of resources, maintained welcoming and well-managed facilities, and cultivated creative school environments. For *educational implement progress*, principals encouraged teacher innovation, fostered collaboration, and supported participatory decision-making in school policy and planning. Regarding *educational objective outcomes*, principals promoted strong teacher-student relationships, effective instructional practices, and positive engagement with parents and the local community, although there remained opportunities to enhance student academic progress and behavior management.

2. Level of Leadership Skills of School Principals. School principals showed highly developed leadership skills. In *building a vision*, they successfully set and

communicated clear goals that aligned stakeholders around a shared purpose. In *providing support*, principals actively invested in teacher development, fostered appreciation, encouraged professional learning, and maintained open communication. For *managing teachers' professional development*, they guided and engaged teachers thoughtfully while promoting relevant learning content and supporting continuous improvement, though some aspects such as systematic evaluation could still be strengthened. In *modeling*, principals exhibited enthusiasm, openness to sharing successes, innovative thinking, and strong team collaboration, serving as effective role models for their staff.

3. Level of Management Skills of School Principals. Principals displayed strong management skills in all measured areas. In *operations*, they promoted flexible teaching methods, encouraged the use of best practices, and supported data-informed instructional strategies. For *monitoring*, principals emphasized systematic process documentation, consistent performance measurement, and effective communication with stakeholders. In *target setting*, principals aligned school and individual goals with system-wide objectives and maintained transparency in performance assessment, though there was some inconsistency in setting appropriately challenging targets. In *people management*, principals recognized and rewarded good teacher performance, promoted merit-based advancement, and made efforts to retain high-performing staff while also addressing underperformance when necessary.

4. School Principals' Performance Rating. Overall, school principals received high performance ratings. The majority were assessed as performing at a very satisfactory level, with a substantial proportion achieving outstanding ratings. Notably, no principals received ratings indicating inadequate performance, reflecting a strong overall standard of professional practice in the district.

5. Predictive Value of Specific Skill Factors on Principal Performance. Analysis revealed that among the measured skill factors, only *target setting* demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with principal performance. However, this relationship was negative, suggesting that overly rigid or unrealistic targets may hinder rather than enhance principal effectiveness. Other skill factors—including educational resource input, educational implement progress, educational objective outcome, building a vision, providing support, managing teachers' professional development, modeling, operations, monitoring, and people management—did not show statistically significant predictive power for performance ratings.

6. Most Parsimonious Combination of Predictors. The study found no parsimonious combination of the measured skill factors that significantly predicted principal performance. While target setting emerged as the only individual factor with predictive value, its negative association with performance indicates that higher levels of target rigidity may contribute to lower performance outcomes, highlighting the need for more flexible, realistic goal-setting practices.

7. Predictive Value of Administrative, Management, and Leadership Skills as Domains. Finally, when considered as broader domains, administrative, management, and leadership skills did not significantly predict principals' performance ratings. While administrative and leadership skills showed slight positive trends, and management skills showed a slight negative trend, none of these relationships were statistically significant within the study's context. This suggests that, independently, these domains did not meaningfully explain variations in performance ratings among principals in the district.

Conclusions

School principals are excellent at many factors of administration and leadership, and they are especially skilled at creating a cooperative and encouraging atmosphere. The findings demonstrate a constant commitment to enhancing academic performance and assisting educators. Although leaders may establish lofty goals, the negative correlation between target setting and performance implies that these goals may occasionally put undue pressure on employees, which could have an impact on performance as a whole. This emphasizes how important it is to set goals in a balanced way, with high standards and attainable results. In the end, the research emphasizes how important great leadership is to establish a healthy school culture and to make sure that goals are defined in a way that supports long-term success for principals and their staff.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the administrative, management, and leadership skills of public elementary school principals in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol, and to help sustain or improve their overall performance:

1. **Enhance Strategic Resource Management.** Principals should prioritize fair, effective, and transparent allocation of resources to support teaching and learning needs. Schools can implement structured audits and participatory planning sessions to identify resource gaps and ensure equitable access for all learners and teachers. Emphasis should also be placed on maintaining school facilities to create welcoming, safe, and conducive learning environments.
2. **Strengthen Innovation and Teacher Collaboration.** Encourage principals to promote a culture of instructional innovation by supporting teacher experimentation with new methods, technologies, and materials. School leaders can establish professional learning communities (PLCs) that foster regular collaboration among teachers, sharing of best practices, and peer mentoring to drive continuous instructional improvement.
3. **Improve Technological Integration and Capacity-Building.** While principals have demonstrated competence in administration, targeted professional development is needed to advance their skills in integrating technology into teaching and school operations. Division offices and local education authorities should provide resources,

training programs, and technical support to help principals and teachers effectively utilize digital tools to enhance student learning.

4. **Develop Participatory Leadership and Decision-Making.** Principals should strengthen participatory decision-making processes by actively engaging teachers, parents, and community stakeholders in policy formulation, planning, and implementation. Structured consultations, feedback mechanisms, and joint planning workshops can build trust, promote shared ownership, and align school initiatives with community expectations.
5. **Promote Balanced, Realistic Goal-Setting Practices.** Given the negative relationship observed between target setting and performance, training programs for principals should focus on setting realistic, achievable, and meaningful goals that motivate staff without creating undue pressure. Emphasis should be placed on collaborative target-setting that considers teacher input, student needs, and contextual factors to ensure goals are both ambitious and attainable.
6. **Enhance Monitoring and Evaluation Systems.** Principals should strengthen systems for process documentation, performance measurement, and continuous improvement. This includes developing clear indicators of success, conducting regular reviews, and ensuring results are communicated effectively to teachers and stakeholders. Training on using data to inform instructional and managerial decisions can help schools sustain improvements and respond flexibly to challenges.
7. **Invest in Comprehensive People Management.** Principals should receive training on recognizing and rewarding good teacher performance, managing underperformance constructively, and supporting career development. Emphasis should be placed on merit-based promotions, mentorship, coaching, and retention strategies to build and maintain a high-performing, motivated teaching workforce committed to student success.
8. **Support Principals' Leadership Development.** School divisions should continue to invest in leadership development programs that enhance principals' abilities to set and communicate clear educational visions, model professional behavior, and maintain strong relationships with staff, students, and the community. Training should emphasize ethical leadership, effective communication, emotional intelligence, and conflict resolution to help principals navigate complex school environments.
9. **Encourage Networking and Collaborative Learning Among Principals.** Establish regular opportunities for principals to share experiences, challenges, and solutions through professional learning networks, workshops, and mentoring programs. By learning from each other's successes and setbacks, principals can adopt effective practices, avoid common pitfalls, and strengthen the overall leadership capacity within the district.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in full adherence to established ethical guidelines to ensure the protection, rights, and welfare of all participants. Prior to the implementation of data collection activities, formal approval was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education. This authorization covered the conduct of surveys and the collection of official performance ratings of school principals.

Participation in the study was strictly voluntary. All respondents were given a clear explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, and expected benefits. Informed consent was obtained from participants before their inclusion, ensuring they understood their rights, including the right to refuse or withdraw from participation at any point without any negative consequences.

The confidentiality and privacy of participants were carefully protected throughout the research process. Personal identifiers were not included in the data collection instruments, and responses were anonymized and aggregated to prevent the identification of individual participants. Performance ratings and survey responses were stored securely and were accessible only to the researcher and authorized personnel.

Furthermore, to maintain trust and respect, participants were assured that all information gathered would be used solely for academic research purposes and that findings would be reported in a way that protects individual identities. After the completion of data analysis, all physical records were disposed of securely through shredding to prevent any unauthorized access or misuse.

The study strictly complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), ensuring that all procedures met national legal requirements for data protection and privacy. Additionally, ethical clearance was obtained from the Holy Name University Ethics Review Committee prior to the conduct of the study, ensuring that all research activities were reviewed and approved for compliance with ethical standards.

A PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM TO STRENGTHEN SCHOOL PRINCIPALS' TARGET-SETTING SKILLS FOR IMPROVED ADMINISTRATION, LEADERSHIP, AND MANAGEMENT

Rationale

Education was highly valued by Filipinos. Effective management, leadership, and administration must exist in school organizations to have high-quality instruction.

Following the study's completion, the researcher discovered that the single construct that predicts a school principal's performance is target-setting. However, they exhibit a negative correlation, with lower performance being linked to higher target settings. In relation to this, as stated in the study of Newman & Azevedo (2013),

excessively high-performance expectations can lead to agent animosity, which will erode the system's credibility and have a detrimental effect on future production. This could therefore lead to a negative performance of the school principal. Additionally, they stressed that the integrity of the performance management system may be jeopardized if principals overlook or engage in unethical behavior when targets are perceived as unachievable.

Thus, the researcher believed that it is essential for school principals to be given an enhancement program, especially in this area where their target-setting skill is claimed to have a negative correlation to their performance.

Program Description

This program will be a two-day activity composed of the following stages:

Proposed Program Title: Collaborative Target Setting and Planning Workshops

Description: The Collaborative Target Setting and Planning Workshops is a 2-day interactive event designed to engage principals, teachers, selected learners, and other stakeholders in the process of setting achievable and meaningful targets for the school. The workshop will foster collaboration through in-depth discussions, and practical exercises on setting SMART targets (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound). The aim is to ensure that all involved parties have a shared understanding of the school's targets in the various areas in the entire school community, creating a unified approach to achieving success. The workshops will also provide opportunities for feedback and reflection on the goal-setting process to improve future planning.

Objectives

The program aims to:

1. Present a clear overview of the expected targets in the various areas (e.g., academic performance, student behavior, resource management, teacher development, etc.) for the entire school year.
2. Revisit the set of targets and all other data necessary in the previous year.
3. Plan collaboratively and revise the targets into SMART and make it known and understandable to all parties.
4. Plan and design a strategic roadmap for the target achievement.
5. Craft collaboratively practical tools for evaluating progress and adjusting targets as needed.

Planning Stage

In the planning stage, which begins two weeks before the workshop, the first step is to set up all logistics, including securing the venue, arranging facilitators, and preparing necessary materials. Clear communication with all participants—principals, teachers, selected learners, and stakeholders—is essential to ensure they understand the objectives and expectations of the event. Invitations are sent out well in advance, with detailed information about the workshop's purpose and schedule. To prepare participants, pre-workshop materials will be provided, allowing them to familiarize themselves with the SMART goal framework and its application. During this stage, the key areas of focus,

such as academic performance, student behavior, resource management, etc., are identified, and data or insights relevant to these areas are gathered. This information will be used during the workshop to inform the goal-setting process.

Implementation Stage

The implementation stage spans the two-day event. On Day 1, the first session will provide an opening and introduction to the workshop, explaining its purpose and structure, followed by team-building activities to foster collaboration among participants. The second session will present the targets for different school areas—academic performance, student behavior, resource management, etc.—with a discussion on their relevance and priority. In the third session, participants will be introduced to the SMART target framework, learning how to create targets that are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. The fourth session will involve a group activity where teams of principals, teachers, learners, and stakeholders will collaborate to create draft SMART targets for various areas of focus. The day will conclude with a reflection and feedback session, allowing each group to present their draft set of targets for evaluation. On Day 2, the first session will focus on target refinement, where feedback from Day 1 will be used to adjust targets to ensure they are both challenging and achievable. The second session will guide participants in creating action plans, defining roles and responsibilities, and timelines to support goal achievement. In the third session, strategies for monitoring progress will be introduced, and tools for evaluating the achievements will be provided. Discussions will also cover how to adjust the targets if needed.

Evaluation Stage

The evaluation stage takes place right after the workshop. During this period, evaluation forms will be distributed to all participants to gather feedback on the workshop, the clarity of the targets, and the overall experience. The feedback will be reviewed carefully to assess what worked well and identify areas for improvement. Any necessary adjustments to the process or materials will be made based on the feedback to improve future workshops. Additionally, follow-up with participants will occur periodically to assess the progress of the targets set during the workshop, offering additional support or guidance if necessary. This ensures that the targets are being pursued effectively and that the workshop's objectives are achieved in the long term.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, E. C. (2008). *Introduction to educational administration: A module*. Port Harcourt: Harey Publications.
- Al-Samarrai, S. (2016). *Assessing basic education service delivery in the Philippines: Public education expenditure tracking and quantitative service delivery study* (No. AUS6799, pp. 1–191). The World Bank.
- Antonakis, J., & House, R. J. (2014). Instrumental leadership: Measurement and extension of transformational–transactional leadership theory. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 25(4), 746–771.
- Bloom, N., Lemos, R., Sadun, R., & Van Reenen, J. (2015). Does management matter in schools? *The Economic Journal*, 125(584), 647–674.
- Elujekwute, E. C. (2019). *Educational management: Concept and theories*. Destiny Ventures.
- Gautam, P. K. (2023). Effect of workforce diversity management on employee performance in educational institutions. *PYC Nepal Journal of Management*, 16(1), 35–54.
- Gordon, S. F. A. (2023). *Teachers' experiences in the school's leadership decision-making processes within school districts* (Doctoral dissertation, Grand Canyon University).
- Grissom, J. A., Egalite, A. J., & Lindsay, C. A. (2021). How principals affect students and schools. *Wallace Foundation*, 2(1), 30–41.
- Hernando-Malipot, M. (2023, January 31). DepEd identifies challenges in basic education through BER 2023. *Manila Bulletin*.
<https://mb.com.ph/2023/01/31/deped-identifies-challenges-in-basic-education-through-ber-2023/>
- Hollingworth, L., Olsen, D., Asikin-Garmager, A., & Winn, K. M. (2018). Initiating conversations and opening doors: How principals establish a positive building culture to sustain school improvement efforts. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(6), 1014–1034.
- Liu, W. S. K. (2024). Global leadership dynamics: Refining executive selection in multinational corporations. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1–45.
- Liu, Y., Bellibaş, M. Ş., & Gümüş, S. (2021). The effect of instructional leadership and distributed leadership on teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction: Mediating roles of supportive school culture and teacher collaboration. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(3), 430–453.
- McNally, S., Schmidt Rivera, L., & Sivropoulos-Valero, A. V. (2024). Do management practices matter in further education? *Economica*, 91(363), 740–769.
- Newman, J., & Azevedo, J. P. (2013). Setting reasonable performance targets for public service delivery. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (6385).
- Oke, J. O. (2016). *Fostering creative thinking skill among building technology students of technical colleges in Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, University Teknologi Malaysia).
- Parojenog, R., & Pabalan, A. P. (2024). *Enhancing basic education standards: A framework for quality advancement*. Available at SSRN 4801978.

- Sebastian, J., Allensworth, E., & Huang, H. (2016). The role of teacher leadership in how principals influence classroom instruction and student learning. *American Journal of Education*, 123(1), 69–108.
- Shaked, H. (2023). Instructional leadership in school middle leaders. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 37(6/7), 1288–1302.
- Tayag, J. R. (2020). Professional learning communities in schools: Challenges and opportunities. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(4), 1529–1534.
- von Bertalanffy, L. (1970). General system theory and psychology. *Toward Unification of Psychology*, 220–223.